

DAMAGE EVOLUTION DURING HIGH-TEMPERATURE OXIDATIVE AGING OF COMPOSITES

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Abstract

The service life of the High Temperature Polymer Matrix Composites (HTPMCs) is limited by thermo-oxidative degradation. Oxidation weakens the material and drives crack formation and propagation. Newly formed crack surfaces allow oxygen to permeate deeper into the structure and accelerate the oxidative degradation. A high-resolution chemo-mechanics model has been developed to study the thermo-oxidative degradation of polymer resins and composites subjected to long-term (thousands of hours) exposure to oxidative environments. This approach entails simulating the time-dependent growth of the surface oxidation layer and analyzing the stress and damage in the material using an oxidation-state dependent constitutive model. This paper describes the effect of fibers on the oxidation and damage growth in a lamina. Since both the oxygen diffusivity and the strength of the lamina are orthotropic, the acceleration of oxidation growth after damage initiation is controlled by the transverse strength and toughness of the oxidized zones in the lamina. We show the long-term oxidation and damage growth in a Carbon/Polyimide composite system subjected to high-temperature isothermal aging.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymer matrix composites (PMCs) used in high-temperature aerospace applications (100-350°C) exhibit limited life due to the accelerated degradation under mechanical, thermal, moisture and oxidative conditions [1- 4]. While both carbon and glass fibers may be stable at operating temperatures under 300°C, the dissolved oxygen reacts with the polymer matrix and degrades the composite. Thermal oxidation degradation has been found to be the main mechanism that degrades the polymer structures. Material oxidation is accompanied by volume changes (polymer shrinkage), and the shrinkage strain depends upon the oxidation state [5]. As the matrix undergoes oxidative shrinkage and the fibers remain dimensionally stable, micromechanical stress develops in the material due to the shrinkage mismatch between these two different phases [1, 5]. As a result, matrix cracking and interface delamination occur during oxidation of composite lamina due to the oxidation-induced stress [7, 8]. Those discrete cracks open up new surfaces and allow oxygen to diffuse deeper into the materials [4, 5]. The high-strain state in the vicinity of cracks accelerates the oxygen diffusion

in the material [9]. Therefore, oxidation growth and damage evolution form a strongly coupled degradation cycle with each accelerating the other [2].

Chemical shrinkage due to oxidation leads to mismatch strain between the fibers and matrix in the lamina. The strain induced by the oxidation and weak oxidized layers in matrix lead to discrete cracks [2, 4]. When cracks propagate perpendicular to fibers through the matrix and go around the fibers in order to grow further into the structure, the damage growth is slower. The cracks are constrained from opening due to fiber bridging, and the crack propagation is retarded. The oxidation layer extent and crack length growth of composite lamina aging at 288°C have been measured [7]. The oxidation growth is orthotropic and expected to be faster along the fiber direction due to higher oxygen diffusivity and lower strength in that direction and the retarded due to fiber bridging in the transverse direction.

The oxidative degradation of polymer resin has been extensively studied by numerical simulation during the last decade. The oxygen diffusion and mechanistic chemistry models [10, 11] describing the reaction chemistry provide considerable insight into the chemical transformation of several polymers. Colin et al. [12, 13] developed a kinetic model coupling the diffusion and consumption kinetics to characterize the oxidation reactions. Recently, several groups began simulating the oxidation degradation of polymers by incorporating mechanistic chemistry models into structural mechanics [14-17].

Research focusing on the effect of cracks on accelerating the oxidation degradation of composites and the coupling between oxidation growth and crack propagation is uncommon. Some studies focused on the oxidation and damage growth of polymer composites include predicting the oxidation-induced damage states (without giving crack surface information) [17] and oxidation-induced delamination (along assumed traction-separation path) [18-20] of polymer composites. Coupled oxidation and damage models have been used to study the thermal oxidation and oxidation-induced damage evolution in polymer composites. The effect of cracks on accelerating the oxidation growth of polymer resin was also studied earlier with a pre-embedded crack and constant crack propagation rate [2]. This paper describes a methodology for determining coupled oxidation growth and crack propagation during isothermal aging of a composite lamina. The effect of fiber bridging on the retardation of oxidative damage growth is also described.

2 A COUPLED OXIDATIVE DEGRADATION MODEL

In order to capture the coupling between oxidation growth and damage evolution of polymer composites, a multi-domain framework has been formulated. An element-free Galerkin simulation determines the morphological changes and the extended finite element method (XFEM) tracks stress and damage [21]. This framework divides the problem into three cooperative simulations, which are executed concurrently. Figure 1 shows a schematic of these three models and the data flow between them. As oxidation takes place over thousands of hours, the time increment at which the simulations are executed is set as one to two hundred hours. The time increment can be reduced, with additional computational burden, to increase the spatial resolution of the prediction. Changes in the morphology of the material are determined over the time increment using an oxidation model, and a snapshot of the oxidation state (ϕ) is determined. The stiffness, strength and toughness at each material point are then updated with appropriate constitutive relationships, and a mechanics model determines the stress state. A damage model then evaluates the damage state (φ) using crack initiation and evolution criteria and communicates it to the oxidation and mechanics models. The cracked boundaries are updated in the oxidation model with appropriate oxygen sorption

boundary conditions, and the oxidation simulation is carried out to the end of the next time increment. These models have been described in detail in earlier papers [2, 4, 5, 15, 22].

Figure 1: The Oxidation-Mechanics-Damage model and parameter flow

The homogenized representative volume element (RVE model) with orthotropic material behaviors was used in prior work. The RVE model has one boundary face exposed to the oxidizing environment and the other five faces (interior faces) are subjected to periodic boundary conditions. The exposed faces have oxygen sorption boundary condition and interior faces have zero-flux condition imposed.

While being exposed to oxidizing environments the boundary surface of polymer composites absorbs oxygen according to Henry's law [15], followed by oxygen diffusion into the material and chemical reaction with polymer resin. When surface material is oxidized, oxygen diffuses deeper and oxidizes more material inside. The oxidation model [15] was developed earlier to compute an oxidation state field $\phi(x,y,z;t)$ of the polymer resin using physics-based simulations of oxygen diffusion and reactions with the resin. In this model, the oxidation reaction is controlled by the oxygen concentration in the material, especially when the dissolved oxygen concentration is much lower than the saturation concentration. Material points with pristine or unoxidized material at any time are assigned an oxidation state value of $\phi(x,y,z;t) = \phi_{un}$, and those with completely oxidized material are assigned $\phi(x,y,z;t) = \phi_{ox}$ with $\phi_{un} > \phi_{ox}$. The material is actively oxidizing in regions, where $\phi_{ox} < \phi < \phi_{un}$. Based on the computed oxidation state field, the oxidation extent can be measured at different aging times and the oxidation growth rate obtained.

The carbon fiber reinforcements greatly increases the oxygen diffusivity of composites in the fiber direction, thus contributing to faster oxidation layer growth in axial direction (L -) of the lamina[1]. In addition, the interphase region between fiber and matrix may be diffusive and contributes to increased oxidation layer growth rates [2]. Any fiber-matrix debonding or transverse cracks also provide additional pathways for oxygen to diffuse into the interior of the material. Therefore, anisotropy was observed for unidirectional composites, and oxidation and damage growth rates are much higher in the axial direction than that in the transverse directions.

The oxidation reaction is controlled by the oxygen concentration in the material, especially when the dissolved oxygen concentration is much lower than the saturation concentration. The dissolved oxygen concentration in the solid (molar volume),

$C(x, y, z; t, T; V_f)$, in the homogenized composite material is a spatially and temporally varying field that depends upon the temperature (T) and fiber volume fraction (V_f). We assume that both diffusion and reaction are strain independent in this analysis. The diffusion-reaction model (governing equation) with orthotropic diffusivity for homogenized material is given by Eq. (1).

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = \left(D_L \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} + D_T \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} + D_Z \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z^2} \right) - R(\phi, T, C, V_f) \quad (1)$$

D_L is oxygen diffusivity along longitudinal direction and D_T and D_Z along transverse directions (T and Z) respectively. The effective oxygen diffusivity of the homogenized composites is interpolated based on the oxidation state as follows:

$$D_{L,T,Z}(\phi, T, V_f) = \left[D_{L,T,Z}^{un}(T, V_f) \left(\frac{\phi - \phi_{ox}}{\phi_{un} - \phi_{ox}} \right) + D_{L,T,Z}^{ox}(T, V_f) \left(\frac{\phi_{un} - \phi}{\phi_{un} - \phi_{ox}} \right) \right] \quad (2)$$

The oxidation reaction rate of polymers is dependent on temperature, oxygen concentration (which is controlled by oxygen diffusion, and the oxidation state [15]). The fiber is considered non-reactive but diffusive at this temperature. The oxidation reaction rate for the homogenized composite with only the resin undergoing oxidation reactions can be written as follows:

$$R(\phi, T, C, V_f) = R_0 \frac{2\beta C}{1+\beta C} \left[1 - \frac{\beta C}{2(1+\beta C)} \right] \left(\frac{\phi - \phi_{ox}}{\phi_{un} - \phi_{ox}} \right) (1 - V_f) \quad (3)$$

The constant β controls the reaction rate dependence on the molar concentration. Temperature dependence of the saturation reaction rate is assumed in Arrhenius form as given by Eq. (4). Since isothermal aging is considered and the saturation reaction rate R_0 is determined at operating temperatures. Thus, the consequences of the Arrhenius assumption on the predictions described in this paper are minimal.

$$R_0 = R_0^* \exp(-R_a/RT) \quad (4)$$

In Eq. (4) R_0^* and R_a are the scaling and activation constants.

The oxidation state variable ϕ indicates the availability of an active polymer sites for reaction. When ϕ reaches the cut-off value ϕ_{ox} , the polymer resin is assumed completely oxidized and the oxygen is assumed to predominantly diffuse in the oxidized polymer rather than react with the polymer. Therefore, the oxidation state variable ϕ tracks the conversion of the polymer into completely oxidized state. The oxidation state is related reaction rate $R(\phi, T, C, V_f)$ and aging time t as follows:

$$\phi = \max \left\{ \phi_{ox}, \left(1 - \int_0^t \alpha(\zeta) R(\zeta) d\zeta \right) \right\} \quad (5)$$

The boundaries of the material exposed to oxygen are subjected to Dirichlet conditions from Henry's law. A saturation concentration, $C_s = S P$, where S is the solubility and P is the partial pressure of the diffusing gas is prescribed on the exposed boundaries. The symmetry boundaries or unexposed surfaces are subjected to flux-free conditions. Eq.(1) is solved over a three-dimensional domain subjected to the boundary conditions using an element-free Galerkin method which has been described in detail in earlier papers [2,4,5,15].

High temperature aging in oxidative environments causes both physical shrinkage (dependent on time t) and chemical shrinkage (dependent on both time t and oxidation state ϕ) in polymer resin. Due to the mismatch of the oxidation-induced strain between oxidized and unoxidized materials, a substantial amount of localized micromechanical stress is

generated. And the oxidation-induced stress drives the damage initiation and crack growth. The oxidation-induced shrinkage is dependent on both aging time t and oxidation state $\phi(x, y, z, t)$ [15]. For an initially mechanically stress-free structure, the oxidation-induced shrinkage strain during oxidative aging, including physical and chemical strain, is divided into time dependent and oxidation-state dependent components. At any material point in the structure, the shrinkage strain increment $\Delta\varepsilon_{L,T,Z}(\phi, \Delta t)$ for the composites with oxidation state $(\phi(x, y, z, t))$ at an arbitrary material point after aging for Δt hours are linearly interpolated based on the oxidation state as follows.

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{L,T,Z}(\phi, \Delta t) = \left[\alpha_{L,T,Z}^{un} \left(\frac{\phi - \phi_{ox}}{\phi_{un} - \phi_{ox}} \right) + \alpha_{L,T,Z}^{ox} \left(\frac{\phi_{un} - \phi}{\phi_{un} - \phi_{ox}} \right) \right] \times \Delta t \quad (6)$$

The deformations and stress fields due to oxidation are then computed everywhere in the structure by solving the governing equilibrium equations subject to appropriate boundary conditions with extended finite element methods (XFEM) [21-23].

Fiber bridging, matrix cracking and interphase debonding are commonly observed in unidirectional composite lamina [4,24]. Hashin's failure criterion [25] was used to identify locations of the damage initiation and the modes of failure. The transverse/ tensile failure mode governs the damage initiation of composite lamina and the acceleration of oxidation can be attributed to the damage growth in this direction. The failure criterion in terms of the stress state at any material point in the analysis domain is required to track the onset of damage.

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_T + \sigma_Z}{F_T^t} \right)^2 + \frac{(\sigma_{TZ}^2 - \sigma_T \sigma_Z)}{(F_{TZ}^s)^2} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{LT}}{F_{LT}^s} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{LZ}}{F_{LZ}^s} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (7)$$

Eq.(4) specifies the transverse failure criterion in which σ_L, σ_T and σ_Z represent the normal stresses in L -, T - and Z - directions respectively, while σ_{LT}, σ_{LZ} and σ_{TZ} represent the shear stresses in L - T , L - Z and T - Z planes respectively. F_T^t is the transverse tensile failure strength of the lamina and a critical property to be estimated for the oxidized regions. F_{LT}^s, F_{LZ}^s and F_{TZ}^s are the shear strengths in L - T , L - Z and T - Z planes respectively.

Damage initiates when transverse/ tensile failure mode is reached and its propagation is controlled by a user-defined traction-separation law [4]. Figure 2 shows the damage evolution law used in this analysis, where the mixed-mode fracture energy G_c is the energy needed for material points to reach full damage. δ_m is the effective separation of crack surfaces in the cohesive failure law. δ_m^o is the effective separation at damage initiation and δ_m^f the effective separation at complete failure (expressed as $\delta_m^f = 2G_c/T_{eff}^o + \delta_m^o$, with T_{eff}^o as the effective traction at damage initiation). A damage process is characterized by the damage state variable ϕ , which is defined based on the separation observed ahead of the crack tip.

During damage evolution the stiffness matrix is reduced based on a damage variable $(= \frac{\delta_m^f(\delta_m^{max} - \delta_m^o)}{\delta_m^{max}(\delta_m^f - \delta_m^o)}; 0 \leq \phi \leq 1)$, and the element is removed when $\phi=1$ (fully damaged) at all integration points of the element. δ_m^{max} is the maximum value of the effective separation δ_m attained during loading history.

Figure 2: Traction-separation law for the cohesive damage growth ahead of the crack tip

3. Coupled Oxidation and Damage Growth along the Fiber Axis

A representative volume element (RVE) was chosen from the lamina with a length of $3000\ \mu\text{m}$, a thickness of $400\ \mu\text{m}$, and a width of $100\ \mu\text{m}$ as shown in Figure 3. The right side of RVE was exposed to oxygen and the oxidation layer grew from right to left through the thickness of the model and along fiber direction (negative L - direction in Figure 3). Figure 4 shows the oxidation and crack growth rates until 2000 hours of aging for a G30/PMR-15 composite lamina. The figure also shows the correlation between model predictions and experimental observations [6]. The lines indicate simulated results and discrete symbols represent experimental observations. The discrete cracking starts from an initial extent of $70\ \mu\text{m}$ at 130 hours and propagates to an extent of $300\ \mu\text{m}$ at 200 hours. We define crack extent as the distance from the crack tip to the exposed edge of the RVE and not the length of the crack. For straight cracks, the crack extent will be the same as the crack length. Oxidation experiments [6,7] showed that the oxidation layers consistently precede the crack front extent. Oxidative shrinkage causes tensile stresses in the oxidized regions and compression in the unoxidized substrate. As the transverse tensile strength for the oxidized material is very low (20 MPa) and the compression strength for unoxidized material is much higher (400 MPa) along the fiber, the cracks arrest at the interface between oxidized and unoxidized zones. However, the newly created crack surfaces have high concentration of dissolved oxygen due to adsorption and oxidized zones grow ahead of the crack tips weakening the material within few hours of aging.

Figure 3: RVE model for a G30/PMR-15 lamina for axial oxidative aging analysis

The simulated results for both oxidation layer growth and crack front extent correlate well with experimental data below 1600 hours of aging. Above 1600 hours, the experimental results do not closely capture the oxidation layer thickness and crack growth. This discrepancy may be attributed to eroded surfaces on the specimens. Erosion leads to under measurement of the oxidation layer sizes in experiments as the exposed surfaces recede into the interior.

Figure 5 and Figure 6 show, respectively, the oxidation and crack growth until 2000 hours of aging. These figures also show the correlation between

Figure 4. Correlation of predictions and experimental observations for oxidation and crack growth in axial direction

model predictions and experimental observations [6]. The lines indicate the results from simulation and discrete symbols represent experimental observations. The discrete crack started from an initial extent of 70 μm at 130 hours and propagated to an extent of 300 μm at 200 hours. The crack extent was defined as the distance from the crack tip to the exposed edge of the RVE, and for straight cracks, the crack extent will be the same as the crack length.

Oxidation experiments [6,7] showed that the oxidation layer extent consistently precedes the crack front. Oxidative shrinkage causes tensile stresses in the oxidized region and compression in the unoxidized region. As the transverse tensile strength for the oxidized material is very low (20 MPa assumed) and the compressive strength for unoxidized material is much higher (400 MPa) along the fiber, the cracks gets arrested at the interface between the oxidized and unoxidized zones. However, the newly created crack surfaces have a high concentration of dissolved oxygen due to adsorption. So the oxidized zone grows fast ahead of the crack tips, weakening the material within a few hours of aging.

Figure 5: Stress states in a G30/PMR-15 lamina under axial oxidation at selected times during isothermal aging

Figure 6: Oxidation layer size and crack extent for G30/PMR-15 lamina under axial oxidation

4. TRANSVERSE OXIDATION WITH FIBER BRIDGING

The damage initiation is governed by stress states (failure criterion), while the damage evolution is controlled by strain states (damage variable) [4]. The oxidized resin has a limited ductility (low fracture toughness) and affinity for brittle fracture [6]. For transverse oxidation, the damage is caused by local shrinkage mismatch between the oxidizing matrix and stable fibers, and cracks propagate surrounding the fibers in a detoured way. Tensile stress is generated in the matrix while compressive stress acts in the fibers, as can be seen in the micromechanical model of Figure 7. The local tensile stress in the matrix drives the crack propagation. Fiber bridging constrains the matrix in the lamina and prohibits the crack from

being initiated, thus reducing the crack propagation and enhancing the oxidation resistance of composite lamina. Higher stress and energy are required to initiate the cracks in the matrix, thus more aging time is needed. Tandon [7] reported the oxidation and crack growth for a G30/PMR-15 composite lamina aging at 288°C for thousands of hours. It takes a longer aging time for a crack to be observed during transverse oxidation, and the cracks grow slowly with oxidation layer extent. Crack initiation is observed after more than 700 hours of aging.

For the homogenized RVE model, however, averaged overall mechanical properties are used, and the local stress concentration information is ignored. As can be seen in the homogenized model in Figure 7, the oxidation-induced stress is uniform in the oxidized region. In this effort, micromechanical model was adopted to study the effect of fiber bridging on retarding the crack growth. The value of fracture toughness for oxidized laminate is also tested.

Figure 7: Stress states comparison between micromechanical and homogenized models

Figure 8: Micromechanical model for a 50% G30/PMR0-15 lamina

For the G30/PMR-15 composites with 50% volume fraction, the diameter of the G30-500 fibers is about 7 μm. A micromechanical model was adopted in this study, with detailed fibers and matrix representation in the model to study the fiber bridging effects. The RVE model has a length of 50 μm (*L*- direction), a width of 4.714 μm and a thickness of 188.97 μm, as shown in Figure 8. The top of the RVE was oxygen exposed, and periodic boundary conditions were applied on the other boundary surfaces. The G30 carbon fibers remain stable during aging while the polymer resin gets oxidized and degrades. The distance between the crack front and the active-reaction zone (oxygen diffusion distance, defined as l_{od}) determines how fast oxygen can be transferred through the crack surfaces into the active reaction zone, and controls the chemical reaction rate of polymer resin with oxygen. The oxidation and crack growth rate after crack initiation are governed by this parameter.

Figure 9: Oxidation and crack propagation of a G30/PMR-15 lamina during transverse aging

Figure 9 shows the crack propagation computed from the micromechanical damage model. As can be seen, for the first ~300 hours after crack initiation, the crack length remains low (below 5 μm) and the crack does not propagate. The crack surfaces have limited areas due to a short crack length and are far from the active reaction zone, as can be seen from Figure 9. The effect of crack opening on accelerating the oxidation degradation can be ignored. This aging period is defined as “crack torpid period”, when the crack length remains low and its effect on accelerating the oxidation degradation is negligible. In this research, the crack torpid period was considered as no crack initiation, and the crack initiation time T_{ck} was defined as the time when the crack starts growing (real crack initiation time plus ~300 hours, as shown in Figure 9). After the crack torpid period ($t > T_{ck}$), the crack starts growing with constant speed and the oxidation is accelerated by crack opening. As can be seen from Figure 10, the oxidation extent leads the crack tip a constant distance (which is oxygen diffusion distance, l_{od}), thus keeping the oxidation and crack growth rate at a nearly constant value. Figure 11 shows the oxidation and damage state after 1100 hours of aging. As can be seen, the crack runs around the fibers and deep into the thickness.

Different values of mixed-mode fracture energy G_c were tested. With higher G_c , a longer oxygen diffusion distance is expected, thus a lower oxidation growth rate. So mixed-mode fracture energy governs the oxidation degradation of composite lamina during transverse aging with fiber bridging.

5. Concluding Remarks

A high-resolution oxidation-mechanics-damage model was developed to study the thermal oxidation degradation of polymer resins and composites subjected to long-term (thousands of hours) exposure to oxidative environments. Using this multi-domain framework, the coupling between oxidation growth and crack propagation was studied. It was found that the long-term oxidative degradation is controlled by the properties of the oxidized layer. This method can be used in the service life prediction of composite structures deployed in oxidizing environments.

A model-based methodology was developed to determine the transverse failure strength of oxidized composite lamina [24] based on results from aging experiments and the multi-domain framework. Based on this value, the damage model can predict the crack propagation

more accurately. This method can be used in predicting the oxidized failure strength of other composite systems. The fiber bridging effect was also studied for the transverse oxidation with the crack surfaces opening along the fiber direction. A micromechanical model was adopted in damage propagation simulations, and local stress and damage states were clearly revealed by the mechanics and damage programs. It was found that during transverse direction oxidation, the crack growth is mainly controlled by the fracture toughness. The crack tip keeps a constant distance from the oxidation extent, accelerating the oxidation growth and keeping it progressing at the same speed as the crack growth.

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